

AL AKHAWAYN UNIVERSITY IN IFRANE

E-banking service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Empirical study on Moroccan consumers

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by

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Chaymae Lougmani, declare that this thesis/project titled, **“E-banking service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Empirical study on Moroccan consumers”** and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

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Abstract

This thesis aims to investigate consumers' perceived quality of electronic banking, as well as its impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Moroccan consumers. To achieve this objective, data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire from 500 respondents, of which 422 were deemed valid for analysis. The respondents are from different cities, genders, ages, educational backgrounds, and occupations. The data collected was analysed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis to evaluate the measurement and structural models. The results of hypothesis testing show that availability, security, relative advantage, and ease of use positively impact perceived service quality, whereas reliability has a negative impact. Perceived service quality has a positive effect on e-satisfaction and e-loyalty. In addition to this, e-satisfaction has a positive impact on e-loyalty. The findings could help us understand where e-banking service providers in Morocco should focus, and that is in improving service quality to enhance the customers satisfaction and loyalty. This topic is significant because of the rapid growth of e-banking services in Morocco and the need to understand the various factors influencing customer loyalty. The study focused on filling the gap in the literature available currently about and in Morocco by exploring the impact of e-banking service quality on e-loyalty and e-satisfaction in this specific context. Our findings suggest that e-banking service providers need to invest in improving service quality, especially reliability, availability, security, relative advantage, and ease of use. In addition to this, e-banking service providers should prioritize customer satisfaction to increase customer loyalty, which could lead to improved business performance.

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1. Introduction:

In the last years, internet banking has become more and more popular not only in Morocco but also in the rest of the planet. In 2020, the number of e-banking platforms users worldwide reached 2.5 billion, and this number is expected to increase to 3.6 billion by 2024 (Juniper Research, 2020). A rapid growth that is related to the advancement of technology, changes in consumer behaviour, and the convenience and cost-effectiveness of digital banking services compared to traditional banking, which we will see in more details later. Morocco is no exception to this rapid growth trend. L'Agence Nationale de Réglementation des Télécommunications (ANRT) found that the number of internet users in the country of Morocco reached 33,86 in 2021 (ANRT, 2021), a 17,78% increase in internet users per year, a steady increase. As internet usage continues to grow in Morocco, the potential for e-banking services to expand automatically increases. According to Bank Al-Maghrib, the central bank of Morocco, the number of internet banking users in the country increased from 1.7 million in 2019 to 2.2 million in 2020 and to 2.8 million in 2021 (Bank Al-Maghrib, 2021). Investigating the factors influencing Moroccan customers attitudes and perceptions of e-banking can be of significant importance.

While previous research has established the importance of service quality, ease of use, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty in the context of e-banking adoption and usage (Liao, Z., & Wong, W. K., 2008; Raza et al., 2020), there is a lack of studies that examine these factors in the specific context of Morocco. This research gap is particularly important as Morocco has unique cultural, social, and economic characteristics that may impact the adoption and usage of e-banking services. Therefore, further investigation is needed to understand the factors influencing Moroccan customers' adoption and usage of e-banking services. This study addresses this research gap by exploring the relationship between service quality, ease of use, e-satisfaction, e-loyalty, and the adoption and usage of e-banking services in Morocco. The findings of this study will contribute to the academic literature on e-banking adoption and usage and provide insights that can be used to inform e-banking service providers and policymakers in Morocco and other developing countries.

As the adoption and usage of e-banking services in Morocco are still lower compared to other countries, the findings of this study can be used by managers, bankers, and policymakers to tailor their services to meet their customers needs and increase their satisfaction and loyalty. It can result in expanding their customer base and increasing revenue. Additionally, the study's insights can be used to develop strategies and design new e-banking products and services that cater for the needs of underserved people promoting financial inclusion in Morocco and contributing to the country's overall economic development. Furthermore, the study's contribution to the academic literature on e-banking adoption and usage in developing countries, particularly in the Moroccan context, can provide valuable knowledge for other developing countries to promote financial inclusion and increase access to financial services. Therefore, this study's contribution to the academic literature can be a reference for future studies and research in e-banking adoption and usage in developing countries.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical foundations

The SERVQUAL Model (Parasuraman et Al., 1988) Service quality is considered to be among the most significant determinants of bank' performance (Saleh et al., 2017). It is defined as the result of a customer's comparison between the expected and the perceived value received from a product or a service (Parasuraman et al., 1988). However, and because of its unique characteristics, it can be difficult to measure it (Hoffman & Bateson, 2002). For this, Parasuraman et al. (1985) suggested a conceptual model to measure the perceived service quality by customers. In this model, many dimensions were included and includes variables such as responsiveness, courtesy, credibility, tangibility, access, communication, and others. The same authors revised their framework to identify the perceived quality as the attitude or global judgment that relate to the superiority of the service (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In addition to that, the same authors developed an instrument known as SERVQUAL, which measures the perceived service quality based on 22 items-scale. Even if this instrument received criticism by many authors (Coulthard, 2004; Newman, 2001), it was widely used in many contributions (Gaur & Agrawal, 2006; Saleem et al., 2016).

2.2. Hypotheses development

Reliability

Reliability is the system's ability to perform banking tasks and services consistently and correctly. It is crucial because customers must trust that their transactions are processed accurately and that their data is kept confidential. Several studies have found that reliability is critical in determining customers' satisfaction and loyalty towards online banking services Indrasari et al. In the scenario where the online banking system is cyber attacks or malfunctions. It is an unfortunate event that can lead to a shift in customer satisfaction, making them less inclined to use the service in the future.

Past research has indicated a correlation between reliability and electronic customer satisfaction (ECS) (Tahtamouni, A. 2022). When the system is reliable, the customer feels satisfied with the service provider. This feeling contributes to increasing the customers' perceived e-banking service quality. Therefore a positive relationship between reliability and perceived service quality in e-banking, Indrasari et al. (2022), Khan et al. (2022), Tahtamouni, A. 2022).

Building on the above discussion and Parasuraman et Al. (1988) 's SERVQUAL model, it is hypothesised that:

H1: reliability positively impacts consumers' perceived e-banking service quality

Availability

Availability is the ability of a system to be accessible and operational when customers need it. Recent studies showed that availability is vital to building customer loyalty and trust for online banking services. For example, a study by Li et al. (2021) found that availability significantly affects customer satisfaction and trust in e-banking. E-banking providers should ensure a highly available and reliable to meet customer expectations and build long-term client relationships. In conclusion, availability is critical to customer satisfaction and loyalty towards e-banking services. Studies by Gunduz & Das (2020) and Khatoon et al. (2020) have shown that customers expect online banking systems to be available and operational at all times. Non availability can result in dissatisfaction and distrust among customers, as Khatoon et al. (2020) demonstrated. Therefore, it is essential for e-banking providers to prioritise the availability of their systems for

a better perception of e-banking service quality and to maintain high levels of customer satisfaction and trust. Accordingly:

H2: Availability positively impacts consumers' perceived e-banking service quality

Security

Customers are more likely to use online banking services when they have a feeling of assurance that their information is safeguarded. Recent studies have also indicated the importance of security for retaining customer loyalty and satisfaction with online banking services. As demonstrated in a recent study conducted by Indrasari, A., Nadjmie, N., & Endri, E. (2022), the impact of security on customers' intention to continue using online banking services was found to be significant. Customer trust and satisfaction with online banking services are influenced by perceived security. However, e-banking providers can get substantial reputational damage and financial losses as a result of security breaches or bad incidents. As shown in a recent study by Perera et al. (2022), security incidents have a significant impact on customers' trust and loyalty towards online banking services. Thus, it is imperative for online banking providers to establish strong security measures and protocols to guarantee the protection and privacy of their customers' data. Chaimaa et al. conducted a study in 2020.

Ultimately, ensuring robust security measures is of utmost importance when it comes to online banking services as it influences the level of trust that customers place in these services, and also affects their willingness to adopt, remain loyal to, and be satisfied with them. Security breaches can have severe consequences, impacting both reputation and finances. It is crucial for online banking providers to prioritise the implementation of robust security measures and protocols. This is essential in order to safeguard customer information, maintain confidentiality, and foster trust and loyalty.

These findings are supported by various recent studies, including those conducted by Angusamy, A., Yee, C. J., & Kuppusamy, J. (2022), Indrasari, A., Nadjmie, N., & Endri, E. (2022), Perera et al. (2022), and Chaimaa et al. (2020). E-banking security is also a key determinant of service quality, as per Parasuraman et Al. (1988) 's SERVQUAL model. Accordingly:

H3: Security positively impacts consumers' perceived e-banking service quality

Relative advantage

Relative advantage refers to on the gains that online banking services provide as compared to traditional banking methods. Sudarsono et al. (2020) suggests that customers' to use of online banking services is positively influenced by relative advantage. Customers' satisfaction with online banking services is therefore impacted by relative advantage (Esmaeili et al. 2021). Additionally, the different advantages of e-banking may also influence customer loyalty and retention. Relative advantage influences customer loyalty towards online banking services Esmaeili et al. (2021). The effect of online banking on e-banking services should not be underestimated. A number of customers evaluate e-banking based measures such as convenience, accessibility, and efficiency. Based on the above, we presume that relative advantage is a key determinant of consumers' perception of online banking. Therefore:

H4: Relative advantage positively impacts consumers' perceived e-banking service quality.

Ease of use

Ease reflects how easy it is for customers to use e-banking platforms. It is one of the key factors that affects customers' adoption and usage of online banking services. According to Wilson et al. (2021), users are more likely to use online banking platforms that are easy to use. Nangin et al. (2020) also suggest that the ease of use has a positive impact on customers' willingness to use online banking services. Ease of use also affects customers' loyalty and retention. Keni (2020) confirm that ease of use positively affects customer loyalty towards online banking services. Customers are likely to stay loyal to e-banking platforms if they are easy to use. Based on the discussion above, we presume that ease of use positively affects customers' perception of online banking services. Therefore:

H5: Ease of use positively impacts consumers' perceived e-banking service quality

E-banking service quality and customer satisfaction

Service quality dimensions play a role in how customers perceive the quality of e-banking services, which in turn affects their satisfaction and loyalty to the service provider (Indriastuti, H., Putri, A. N. O. D., Robiansyah, R., & Anwar, H. (2022). Studies show that the quality of e-banking services has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. A study (Raza et al. 2020) discovered a strong correlation between perceived service quality and customer satisfaction.

Another study by El Mosallamy and Metawie (2022), discovered the same thing, customer loyalty towards online banking services impacts positively perceived service quality. It is important to understand how the customers perceive the quality of online banking as it has a direct impact on their satisfaction and loyalty not only towards the e-service but also towards the provider. When service quality is seen as excellent, the customers are more inclined to use it again and recommend it to other people around them. However, if customers perceive the service quality as subpar, they may be inclined to switch to a competitor or discontinue using e-banking services altogether. Thus, it is essential to grasp and handle customer perceptions of e-banking service quality in order to achieve success and maintain the longevity of e-banking services.

Building on the above, here is the hypothesis proposed:

H6: Consumers' perception of e-banking service quality positively impacts customer satisfaction

H7: Consumers' perception of e-banking service quality positively impacts customer loyalty

Consumers satisfaction & customer loyalty

Customer satisfaction is the degree to which customers are pleased with the quality, efficiency, and overall performance of their bank's electronic banking services. This satisfaction is often measured by

reliability, security, fulfilment, ease of use and responsiveness Oghenechuko Salome et al. (2022). Research by Zhang and Liang (2021) spotlights the importance of personalisation in e-banking services. Customers increasingly expect banks to provide tailored experiences that meet their individual needs and preferences. In order to maintain customer satisfaction, banks need to continuously improve their e-banking services and ensure that they align with customer expectations.

Customer loyalty refers to customers' willingness to remain with their bank and continue using its e-banking services over time. This loyalty is often measured by user behaviours such as the frequency and volume of transactions, positive word-of-mouth, and resistance to switching to competitors. (Arshad Khan, M., & Alhumoudi, H. A. 2022) note that customer loyalty can be influenced by factors such as the quality of e-banking services, the level of trust between the bank and the customer, and the perceived benefits of using the bank's services. Banks that

successfully maintain customer loyalty are likelier to see positive business outcomes, such as increased revenue and market share.

Perceived e-banking service quality is critical to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Studies by Beshir, E. S., & Zelalem, B. A. (2020) and Tumewah, E., & Kurniawan, Y. (2020) show that high-quality e-banking services positively influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. Banks prioritising developing best-in-class e-banking services are more likely to retain customers and increase engagement with e-banking platforms.

H8: Consumers' satisfaction with e-banking positively impacts their loyalty

Building on the above discussion, the following conceptual model was proposed:

Fig 1. Conceptual framework

3. Research Methods

3.1. Procedures

According to the “Rapport annuel sur les infrastructures des marchés financiers et les moyens de paiement, leur surveillance et l'inclusion financière" for the years 2020 and 2021”, published by Bank Al-Maghrib, the use of internet banking in Morocco has been increasing, with significant growth in the number of transactions conducted through electronic channels, including internet banking and mobile banking. The first report (2020) highlights that internet banking transactions reached 205 million in 2020, compared to 149 million in 2019, representing an increase of approximately 38% year-on-year. Similarly, the second report (2021) shows a 30.2% growth in transactions conducted through electronic channels in 2021 compared to the previous year, with a 56.6% growth in transactions through mobile channels. The reports suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic has played a role in accelerating the adoption of internet banking and other digital financial services in Morocco, as people sought to avoid physical contact and adhere to social distancing guidelines. Overall, the internet banking situation in Morocco seems to be thriving, reflecting the increasing importance of digital financial services in the country's financial landscape.

To ensure the practicality of our study, we utilised a nonprobability sampling method that combined self-selecting and snowballs sampling techniques. The questionnaire was distributed through various social media platforms, such as Messenger and Facebook, as a voluntary selection method where individuals expressed their interest in participating in the study (Saunders et al., 2012). We also emailed the questionnaire, requesting that contacts complete it and forward it to others. Given the widespread use of social media in Morocco, we considered the online questionnaire administration suitable. Official statistics from (NapoleonCat 2020) show that in August 2020, the number of Facebook users in Morocco exceeded 21,020,000 (56.3% of the entire population), while there were 18,700,000 Messenger users (50.1% of the entire population).

The filtering process involved using two questions to narrow the pool of respondents to a group that met specific criteria: having a bank account and having experience with online banking activities. We received survey responses from 500 individuals, out of which 422 responses were

deemed adequate after filtering. Over three months, from May to July 2020, 500 respondents completed the questionnaire, out of which 422 responses were considered valid (84.4%). The remaining 78 responses were rejected due to incomplete answers, having the same response to all questions, or needing prior internet banking experience.

3.2. Measures

We presented the questionnaire scales and items in French, frequently used among Moroccans (Chetioui et al., 2020a, 2020b). We used the back-translation technique (Brislin, 1986) to translate the items from English to French. In the Appendix, we can see that we adapted all constructs from existing literature, making minor adjustments. We used a five-point scale that ranges from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (means strongly agree) to measure all constructs. At the end of the questionnaire (Table 1), we included demographic questions regarding gender, age, city, employment status, income, and education. Before testing the structural model, we analysed the measured model to establish its reliability and validity of the measurement model. It included an analysis of internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. These analyses aimed to make sure that our questionnaire was reliable and valid.

4. Results

As illustrated in Table 1, The data shows that the sample is pretty split between men and women, with 215 (50.95%) female and 207 (49.05%) male respondents. It indicates that the study has a balanced representation of both genders. The additional data shows that most respondents are between 18 and 25 years old, with 218 (51.66%) falling within this age range. The next largest age group is 26-30, with 78 (18.48%) respondents. The remaining respondents are spread relatively evenly across the older age groups, with 64 (15.17%) between 31-40 years old and 62 (14.70%) over 41 years old. Most respondents have a Master's degree, with 162 (38.39%) falling within this category. This is followed by 127 (30.09%) respondents with a Bachelor's degree (Bac+3) and 65 (15.40%) with a Bac+2 degree. Only 26 (6.16%) respondents have a high school diploma (Bac or less), while 42 (9.95%) fall into the "Others" category, which likely includes those with vocational or technical degrees or other types of certifications. Concerning employment status, Most respondents are students, with 188 (44.55%) falling into this category.

The next largest group are those who work as employees, with 126 (29.86%) respondents. Other groups are represented to a lesser extent, with 51 (12.08%) respondents working as managers, 35 (8.29%) as entrepreneurs, and 22 (5.21%) currently looking for employment. As for the buying preference of the sample population, we have 214 (50.71%) respondents indicating a preference for online shopping and 208 (49.29%) indicating a preference for in-store shopping. The geographic distribution of the sample population shows the majority of respondents living in Casablanca (173, 40.76%), followed by Meknes (63, 14.93%), Rabat (57, 13.51%), and Marrakech (28, 6.64%). Many respondents (101, 23.97%) are from other locations not specified in the data.

Table 1. Respondents profile (n=422)

Measure	Item	N	Percentage
Gender	Male	207	49.05%
	Female	215	50.95%
Age	18-25	218	51.66%
	26-30	78	18.48%
	31-40	64	15.17%
	41+	62	14.70%
Education	Bac or less	26	6.16%
	Bac +2	65	15.40%
	Bac+3	127	30.09%
	Master's	162	38.39%
	Others	42	9.95%
Occupation	Student	188	44.55%
	Employee	126	29.86%
	Manager	51	12.08%
	Entrepreneur	35	8.29%
	Looking for employment	22	5.21%
Buying preference	Online	214	50.71%
	In-store	208	49.29%

City of residence	Casablanca	173	40.76%
	Meknes	63	14.93%
	Rabat	57	13.51%
	Marrakech	28	6.64%
	Others	101	23.97%

4.1. Assessment of the measurement model

The PLS results show that all the loadings of the items on their respective constructs are above the threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019), indicating satisfactory convergent validity. The composite reliability (CR) values are also above the recommended 0.7 thresholds (Chin, 1998; Hair et al., 2010; Henseler et al., 2009), suggesting good internal consistency reliability. Moreover, each construct's average variance extracted (AVE) values are above the recommended threshold of 0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), indicating adequate convergent validity. Therefore, the measurement model exhibits acceptable reliability and validity properties (See tables 2 & 3).

Table 2. Item Loadings

	Availability	E-satisfaction	Ease of use	Perceived service quality	Relative advantage	Reliability	Security	e-loyalty
AVAIL1	0.932							
AVAIL2	0.925							
AVAIL3	0.839							
EOU1			0.841					
EOU2			0.900					
EOU3			0.901					
LOY1								0.937
LOY2								0.933
LOY3								0.938
RA1					0.919			
RA2					0.911			
RA3					0.814			
REL1						0.926		
REL2						0.924		
REL3						0.918		
SAT1		0.940						

SAT2	0.914		
SAT3	0.928		
SEC1			0.867
SEC2			0.875
SEC3			0.918
SEC4			0.911
SERQ1		0.884	
SERQ2		0.886	
SERQ3		0.868	

Table 3. Composite reliabilities, Cronbach Alpha and Average variance extracted (n=422)

Constructs	Cronbach Alpha	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
Availability	0.882	0.927	0.809
E-satisfaction	0.919	0.949	0.860
Ease of use	0.855	0.912	0.776
Perceived service quality	0.854	0.911	0.774
Relative advantage	0.857	0.913	0.779
Reliability	0.913	0.945	0.851
Security	0.915	0.940	0.798
e-loyalty	0.929	0.955	0.876

The HTMT values for all the construct pairs are less than the recommended threshold of 0.9 (Garson, 2015; Tenenhaus et al., 2005; Zhao et al., 2010), indicating satisfactory discriminant validity between the constructs. These results suggest that the measures of each construct are more highly correlated with their own measures than with the measures of other constructs, which supports the convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs in the model. Therefore, we can conclude that the measurement model exhibits good discriminant validity properties.

Table 4. Discriminant validity (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratios-HTMT)

	Availability	E-satisfaction	Ease of use	Perceived service quality	Relative advantage	Reliability	Security	e-loyalty
Availability								
E-satisfaction	0.562							
Ease of use	0.607	0.828						
Perceived service quality	0.598	0.799	0.882					
Relative advantage	0.480	0.761	0.873	0.729				

Reliability	0.559	0.560	0.602	0.564	0.606		
Security	0.554	0.599	0.612	0.626	0.604	0.824	
e-loyalty	0.534	0.811	0.814	0.762	0.854	0.600	0.659

4.2. Assessment of the structural model

We used the coefficient of determination (R-square), as suggested by Hair et al. (2017). The R-square values indicate the proportion of variance explained by the external constructs which are the independent variables, namely "Availability," "Ease of Use," "Relative Advantage," "Reliability," and "Security," on the internal constructs "Perceived Service Quality," "e-Satisfaction," and "e-Loyalty. Table 5 shows that the R-square values for perceived service quality, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty are 0.613, 0.502, and 0.608, respectively. These values indicate that the model explains a high proportion of the variance in these constructs. Overall, the assessment of the structural model suggests that the proposed model has a good fit with the data and has high predictive power for the endogenous constructs.

Table 5. Coefficient of determination

	R Square
Perceived service quality	0.613
E-satisfaction	0.502
e-loyalty	0.608

Our research explains 61.3% of the valuation in perceived service quality through the conceptual model. First, ease of use presented the strongest effect on perceived service quality ($\beta=0.548$; $P\text{-value}<0.01$), approving H5. Our results also confirm that relative advantage ($\beta=0.185$; $p=0.003$), security ($\beta=0.172$, $p\text{-value}=0.02$), and availability ($\beta=0.128$; $p\text{-value}=0.003$) as main determinans of perceived service quality, approving H2, H3,H4. Still, reliability was found to have no significant impact on perceived service quality (please refer to table 6).

The R-squared value for e-satisfaction is 0.502, which means that 50.2% of the variance in e-loyalty can be explained by e-satisfaction through the conceptual model. Perceived service quality has a strong positive relationship with e-satisfaction ($\beta=0.708$; $p\text{-value}<0.01$); the results provide strong evidence supporting the hypothesis that perceived service quality is positively related to e-satisfaction.

As for the R-squared value for e-loyalty is 0.069, this means that the variance in e-loyalty can be explained by the model at 60.8%. E-satisfaction has a strong positive effect on e-loyalty (beta=0.539; p-value<0.01), confirming H8. Perceived e-service quality positively impacts e-loyalty (beta=0.299; p-value<0.01), approving H7.

Table 6. Hypothesis testing

Hypotheses	Relationships	Beta	STDEV	T-statistics	P-values
H1	Reliability -> Perceived service quality	-0.03 3	0.050	0.668	0.504
H2	Availability -> Perceived service quality	0.128	0.043	2.997	0.003
H3	Security -> Perceived service quality	0.172	0.055	3.103	0.002
H4	Relative advantage -> Perceived service quality	0.185	0.061	2.411	0.003
H5	Ease of use -> Perceived service quality	0.548	0.066	8.300	0.000
H6	Perceived service quality -> E-satisfaction	0.708	0.033	21.471	0.000
H7	Perceived service quality -> e-loyalty	0.299	0.051	5.838	0.000
H8	E-satisfaction -> e-loyalty	0.539	0.057	9.411	0.000

5. Discussion and conclusions

The study found that ease of use was the strongest factor influencing perceived service quality, followed by relative advantage, security, and availability. However, reliability was found to have no significant impact on perceived service quality. Based on the previous studies in the literature view, there is a generally accepted positive relationship between reliability and perceived service quality in e-banking (Indrasari et al., 2022, Khan et al., 2022, Tahtamouni, 2022). However, in the current study, it was found that reliability did not have a significant impact on perceived service quality in the conceptual model. It could be due to various reasons; the sample characteristics presented in the table may indirectly impact the relationship between reliability and perceived service quality in several ways. The samples used in the previous studies may have differed from those used in our study, which may have resulted in different findings. For example, the previous studies may have used a larger or more diverse sample than ours, which could have resulted in more representative findings.

Based on the samples' descriptive statistics, more respondents prefer buying online than in-store. It could indicate that the sample is more familiar with and comfortable using online services, which may influence their perceptions of reliability. Over half of the respondents (51.66%) are aged between 18 and 25. This age group have different expectations and perceptions of service

quality compared to older people. For example, younger customers maybe prioritise speed and convenience over reliability, which can explain why reliability was not a significant factor in their perception of service quality. As for Education, our results show that over half of the respondents have a Master's degree (38.39%), which suggests that the sample may be highly educated and have different expectations of service quality compared to less educated customers. Highly educated customers may have a greater understanding of technology and be more forgiving of minor reliability issues, which could explain why reliability was not a significant factor in their perception of service quality. Overall, the sample's demographic characteristics could indirectly impact the relationship between reliability and perceived service quality by influencing customer expectations, perceptions, and priorities. However, further analysis would be needed to confirm these hypotheses and determine why reliability was not found to be a significant factor in the study.

The previous studies may have used different research methods or measures to assess the reliability and perceived service quality variables, which may have affected the findings. In this study, we did not use any control variables; this could be why H1 was not supported through the conceptual model. Based on the literature review, we have seen that H2 (Availability -> Perceived service quality) was supported in other studies, which goes hand in hand with our study findings. Some possible factors could be that customers may have certain expectations regarding the availability of a service. We have observed from other studies that customers expect a service to be available 24/7 or during certain hours of the day. If a service meets or exceeds these expectations, customers will likely perceive it as high quality (Gunduz & Das, 2020; Li et al., 202; Khatoon et al., 2020). Therefore, customer expectations may drive the relationship between availability and perceived service quality. The hypothesis validation could also be related to back-end development. In financial institutions, a large number of data needs to be fetched from the server; this could easily provoke a delay in loading the information that the customer sees on their device. Loading speed could have a massive impact on customer perception of service quality. Therefore, the back-end development of the service may drive the relationship between availability and perceived service quality. Customers' experience and familiarity with a service can also impact their perception of its availability. If customers have prior experience using a service and have learned how to use it over time, they might not perceive availability as someone who started using it recently.

Hypothesis H3 states that security has a positive relationship with perceived service quality. The beta value of 0.172 indicates a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. The p-value of 0.002 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant which means unlikely to have occurred by chance. This finding suggests that customers who perceive higher levels of security in their online banking experience are likely to perceive the overall service quality as better. Security is vital in building trust and confidence in online banking, which can contribute to a positive customer experience. Studies by Angusamy, A., Yee, C. J., & Kuppusamy, J. 2022, Indrasari, A., Nadjmie, N., & Endri, E. 2022, and P., & Rizqi, P. M. 2022 have shown that security significantly affects customers' intention to continue using online banking services and positively influences customer trust and satisfaction. We know that online banking is subject to theft and fishing attacks. Security measures such as encryption, authentication, and fraud detection can help build customers' trust and confidence in their online banking experience. Banks can mitigate these risks and protect their customers' data and transactions by implementing adequate security measures. Risk mitigation can contribute to a positive customer experience, as customers are less likely to encounter problems or issues related to security. There are ways to show the customers that measures are put in place, like the security encryption sign that banks show on their online platforms and two-factor authentication to show the customer that their data is secured.

Security is critical in shaping customers' perceptions of service quality in internet banking. In today's digital age, customers expect their banks to provide a high level of security for their online transactions. Customers are more likely to trust a bank that takes security seriously and invests in robust security measures. By meeting these expectations, banks can create a positive customer experience and enhance customer loyalty.

As for H4, our results indicated that the strength and direction of the relationship between these two variables. A beta coefficient of 0.185 suggests a moderate positive relationship, which means that as relative advantage increases, so does perceived service quality. In internet banking, relative advantage refers to the extent to which this service is perceived to offer benefits or advantages over traditional banking methods, such as visiting a physical bank branch or using an ATM. Some potential advantages of internet banking include convenience, accessibility,

time-saving, and cost-effectiveness. For example, internet banking allows customers to perform banking transactions from the comfort of their homes, at any time, without visiting a bank branch physically. It saves customers time and effort and is incredibly convenient for those with busy schedules or mobility issues. Additionally, internet banking is more cost-effective than traditional banking, as it does not involve fees associated with physical transactions or require as many staff resources. Understanding the relative advantage of internet banking is essential for banks and financial institutions that seek to attract and retain customers in a continuously competing market. By identifying the unique benefits and advantages of internet banking, they can develop effective marketing strategies that target specific market segments and address potential concerns or risks associated with the service. Additionally, they can continue to innovate and improve the service to maintain its relative advantage over time. Studies by Esmaili, A., Haghgoo, I., Davidavičienė, V., & Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė, I. (2021), Sudarsono, H., Nugrohowati, R. N. I., & Tumewang, Y. K. (2020), Owusu, G. M. Y., Bekoe, R. A., Addo-Yobo, A. A., & Otieku, J. 2021, support the importance of relative advantage in online banking.

As for H5 (Ease of use -> Perceived service quality), The hypothesis states that ease of use is positively related to perceived service quality. Ease of use can significantly impact perceived service quality for several reasons. Navigation, for instance, is critical in changing customer perception towards a user-friendly platform; the user interface should be intuitive and user-friendly, with clear labelling and easy-to-find and use functionalities and functions. Speed is also another factor that impacts the customer's perception.

6. Study' Implications

Based on our research findings and analysis, we recommend that banks should focus some of their attention on improving their customers' perceived e-banking service quality. They can invest time, resources and money into developing user-friendly and accessible online banking platforms that give the users and customers convenience, and security. E-banking platform should be easy to use without a tutorial but, in some instances, banks should educate their customers to use online banking services securely to enhance their confidence and trust in the service.

To improve customer satisfaction and loyalty towards e-banking services, banks should focus on delivering high-quality services that meet customers' expectations and needs. It can be achieved by regularly monitoring and measuring customers' perceptions of e-banking service quality and using their feedback to improve service delivery.

Finally, to make their customers trust them, banks have to make sure their e-banking services are secure, reliable, and transparent. Banks have to be credible in the eyes of their customers. They have to implement a security that is highly robust and measures to protect customers data and information and provide accurate information about their services and any of their charges to customers clearly and transparently. In summary, banks should prioritise the development of user-friendly and secure e-banking services, regularly monitor and improve service quality based on customer feedback, and build trust and credibility with and for their customers.

7. Limitations and future research

There are many limitations to this study, given that it was conducted in the specific context of Morocco and with a small sample of customers. As a consequence, the results may only apply to some populations and contexts beyond Morocco. Other populations and contexts may have different cultures, behaviours, and attitudes towards e-banking services, which could affect the results.

The study relied on self-reported measures of the constructs, which can be subject to a lot of biases and may not fully capture the complex nature of these. This limitation implies that the study gathered data on the model constructs using a self-reported survey/questionnaire, which can be influenced by various biases. For instance, people prefer to see themselves under a good light or may they are not remember their exact experience when they used the e-banking services. In addition, the complexity of e-banking services, e-loyalty, and e-satisfaction can be influenced by a range of factors beyond what the questionnaire has captured. These factors can include brand perception and other variables. Hence, the study's findings may not fully represent the levels of e-loyalty and e-satisfaction among customers of e-banking services in Morocco.

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